

Entrepreneurship as a tool to facilitate job placement for civil engineering students

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Abstract

Traditionally, civil engineering professionals have worked for public institutions and large construction companies. Nowadays, recent graduates of civil engineering have problems finding their first job despite the requirements of the degree. Creativity, collaboration, persuasion and emotional intelligence are the essential soft skills needed. Unfortunately, none of them appears in the civil engineering curriculum.

This work proposes to conduct the creation of small cooperative teams of students to face different challenges in line with the syllabus of one or several subjects. Thanks to this, students can increase the number of competencies developed during their academic life at the university. Nevertheless, they are able to apply technical knowledge while they gain professional experiences, improve their soft skills and enhance the ability to understand, use and manage their own emotions through active learning. Incorporating real-life technical problems, already solved or not, from different companies is the key to establishing alliances with enterprises that connect hard and soft skills. In this way, the quality of the grade can be improved while the students keep learning key competencies of the subject allowing them to gain skills and professional experience. Furthermore, this activity can be the beginning of a start-up in an academic environment.

This research has shown the need for the development of soft skills in civil engineering students, both undergraduate and master's degrees, to promote entrepreneurship and self-employment as job opportunities. The creation of the teams, their management, the resolution of the different problems from real-life situations or adapted, the connection with different companies and institutions and the presentation of the results can be the key to the holistic development of future professionals. Including the possibility of entrepreneurship, since all the students questioned considered that they have improved their entrepreneurial competencies thanks to this experience.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Entrepreneurship; Start-Up; Soft Skills.

1 Introduction

Both the current and future generations of civil engineers will not find it sufficient to assimilate the curriculum content related to the technical knowledge of road design, dam maintenance or port management. Unemployment rates among civil engineering graduates are on the rise and there are more and more civil engineering schools. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce knowledge related to entrepreneurship as well as the development of soft skills as a differentiator for the subsequent employability of graduates.

An important aspect to justify this need is the unemployment rate of close to 5% in the year 2020 along with the low rate of Spanish university graduates who develop their professional activity from self-employment (Garcia-Barba et al., 2020). Furthermore, the European Union has set as a strategic objective within the ET2020 document "Increasing creativity and innovation, including entrepreneurship, at all levels of education and training" (Weber, 2012). Therefore, this innovative action is understood and explained within this objective. Also considering, entrepreneurship is a complex and extensive process ranging from the generation of the idea, the process of elaboration and maturation of the idea, the output to the real world, as well as the evaluation of the process to complete the action performed.

From a formal point of view, there is more and more research and in-depth study of the phenomenon of entrepreneurship and the concept itself, and most developing and developed countries are now beginning to clearly link entrepreneurship education and training (Matlay, 2008). It is clear, as already mentioned, that the concept of entrepreneurship education is much broader than just entrepreneurship training content. As Osorio and Duarte (2011) state, economic sciences have a functional view, of what to do; human sciences focus on the

subject, they are interested in who and why; whereas management sciences apply to the process, how. We can complete the definition of the concept of entrepreneurial activity as the management of radical and discontinuous change, or strategic renewal regardless of whether this strategic renewal occurs within or outside existing organisations, and regardless of whether it results in a new business (de Haro et al., 2019).

Of course, as Timmons (2003) suggests, the myth that entrepreneurs are born has evolved, leading to the consensus that entrepreneurship, like any other discipline, can be learned. If we delve a little deeper, entrepreneurship includes the study of the sources of opportunities, the processes of discovering, evaluating and exploiting opportunities, and the people who discover, evaluate and exploit them. Entrepreneurship does not require, but may include the creation of new organisations (Shane & Venkataraman, 2003). Furthermore, we should understand these entrepreneurial competencies as "the set of knowledge, skills, abilities and aptitudes necessary for the effective work of an individual in a specific work environment" (Savanevičienė et al., 2008). Entrepreneurship should therefore be approached holistically by acquiring the set of competencies and we can understand it from Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1987), the individual's attention is directed towards the entrepreneurial phenomenon, instilling certain knowledge and skills to be able to create entrepreneurial activity, which facilitates and supports the emergence of entrepreneurial behaviours. Although the observation method is not the only approach to internalise and reproducing these behaviours (Arriaga et al., 2006). For instance, learning by doing is one of the keys to the development of these entrepreneurial skills (Lăcătuș & Stăiculescu, 2016).

The aim of this research is to evaluate the influence that the development of entrepreneurial projects has on the development of soft skills for entrepreneurship in students, as well as the improvement of the results in the subject itself by carrying out a realistic and viable project. Students to promote entrepreneurship and self-employment as job opportunities. The creation of small cooperative teams of students to face different real-life challenges while they keep learning key competencies of a subject will improve their soft skills and professional experience, including the possibility of entrepreneurship as a tool to facilitate job placement thanks to having an integral vision of the project and not only a technical one. Even, in the future, they will be able to identify any project as a business opportunity.

2 Method

2.1 Context and student profile

This experience was implemented in the subject Maritime Traffic and Port Operation, optative framed in the first four-month period of the second year of the Master's degree in Civil Engineering, during the academic year 2020-21 and 2021-22. The purpose of this subject is to familiarize and train students in the understanding of the knowledge derived from maritime traffic and port operations. The course is carried out through theoretical and practical lessons on problems with practical cases related to maritime traffic and port operations. It has 3 credits ECTS: 1,20 Practical credits and 1,80 Distance-based hours. The entrepreneurial project is fully developed during the first quarter of the second academic year of the Master.

The students of Master's degree in Civil Engineering have a deeper understanding of the multiple constraints of technical and legal nature arising in public work construction. Moreover, it is designed to boost their ability to use proven methods and technologies in order to achieve greater efficiency in public work construction. In addition, the students who are attending this course have already passed subjects in the civil engineering degree that previously develop the basic knowledge to create entrepreneurial projects, such as *Engineering and Business*, *Works for organisation and occupational health and safety* or *Urban planning and environment* (Table 1). Therefore, they should already be able to tackle the professional world of civil engineering and the construction business.

2.2 Description of the experience

The aim of the experience is to develop teamwork to solve an open problem so that students are able to adopt a creative and innovative solution ensuring sustainability from an economic, financial and technological point of view. The problems or projects to be solved are connected to real problems and can lead to public-private

collaboration, thus allowing the creation of a learning environment that leads to the development of skills and attitudes in the profile of civil engineering students.

Through the entity that manages the ports of Valencia, Sagunto and Gandía, the Port Authority of Valencia and the Open Innovation Hub of Valenciaport, a series of real challenges will be established that must be solved as sustainable projects from an integral point of view. The Port of Valencia is also one of the leaders in container transport in the Mediterranean Sea, reaffirming itself as well as "strengthening its leadership position as a reference and strategic hub of the Mediterranean in the management of goods and traffic, its commitment to sustainability and the environment, digitalisation and transparency". Therefore, each academic year will include a series of challenges related to the sustainable mobility of people and goods, the development of a competitive offer of infrastructures and services, as well as the fight against climate change. In short, the aim is to develop solutions and business models to achieve a smart, green and resilient port in the future (Figure 1). The different development proposals should be connected to the items given in Figure 1, related to circularity, planning, management and operations. In this way, we connect the development of entrepreneurial ideas considering social and environmental aspects.

Table 1: Curriculum of the Undergraduate degree in Civil Engineering at the University of Alicante. In bold are the subjects that previously develop the basic knowledge to create entrepreneurial projects.

FIRST-YEAR	ECTS
FUNDAMENTALS OF MATHEMATICS IN ENGINEERING I	6
FUNDAMENTALS OF PHYSICS IN CIVIL ENGINEERING	6
FUNDAMENTALS OF CHEMISTRY IN CIVIL ENGINEERING	6
FUNDAMENTALS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY	6
ENGINEERING AND BUSINESS	6
FUNDAMENTALS OF MATHEMATICS IN ENGINEERING II	6
MECHANICS FOR ENGINEERS	6
GRAPHIC EXPRESSION I	6
FUNDAMENTALS OF MATHEMATICS IN ENGINEERING III	6
GEOLOGY APPLIED TO CIVIL ENGINEERING	6
SECOND-YEAR	
STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS I	7.5
CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS I	6
GRAPHIC EXPRESSION II	7.5
HYDRAULICS AND HYDROLOGY	9
SOIL AND ROCK MECHANICS	6
FURTHER MATHEMATICS	6
STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS II	6
CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS II	6
TOPOGRAPHY AND PHOTOGRAMMETRY	6
THIRD-YEAR	
GEOTECHNICS AND FOUNDATIONS	6
ELECTRICAL TECHNOLOGY AND LIGHTING ENGINEERING	6

CONSTRUCTION PROCEDURES AND MACHINERY IN PUBLIC WORKS	6
URBAN PLANNING AND THE ENVIRONMENT	6
METALLIC STRUCTURES	6
REINFORCED AND PRE-STRESSED CONCRETE STRUCTURES	6
WORKS ORGANISATION AND OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY	6
+COMPULSORY SUBJECTS: PUBLIC WORKS, HYDROLOGY OR TRANSPORT AND SERVICES	18
FOURTH-YEAR	
FINAL PROJECT	12
+COMPULSORY SUBJECTS: PUBLIC WORKS, HYDROLOGY OR TRANSPORT AND SERVICES	48

Figure 1: Challenges in which the different projects will be included

The development of the entrepreneurial project can be structured in four steps (Figure 2) It begins with the presentation of the challenges for the academic year. After the first phase of research on the different proposals by the teams, the choice of the problem or project is made.

Figure 2 Steps of the entrepreneurial project

The next phase has to do with the part of in-depth research of the problem, academic and professional review of the subject studied and the ideation of proposals that solve the problem with the characteristics mentioned.

The following step is related to the realization of the ideas generated in the previous stage, the development of the project from the technical point of view and the application of the Business Model Canvas (Figure 3). It resolves aspects such as the value proposition, or what our solution brings to the table that is different from what was being done before (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010).

Abstract:

Figure 3: Business Model Canvas adapted for the entrepreneurial project.

Moreover, it considers the customer segment or, depending on the type of project, the different users. It also includes the relationship established with the customers and how our solution reaches these users. This document reflects the activities and key resources that are necessary for our proposal to work as well as the possible alliances that can or should be established for it to work properly. Finally, it considers its economic balance, both in terms of costs and revenues. We will also include the social and environmental impact of the project itself. In this way, students solve the proposed problems from a technical point of view but are able to understand their economic feasibility. Thus, they can understand how their solution would work from a business point of view, giving it the form of a business idea and almost a business plan, one of the first steps to entrepreneurship through this model. Finally, the project is presented for its evaluation both by the teachers

of the course and by the organizations or entities that have proposed the issues and problems to be solved in order to assess both from the technical and academic point of view the different solutions provided.

2.3 Evaluation

For the global evaluation of the Project, not only concerning the given solution but also to measure the whole development of the project from an integral point of view, the following evaluation rubric is proposed for the different teams that carry it out, establishing the score from 0 to 10 and determining a weight percentage of influence of the value of each item, being the final grade the weighted grade (Table 2).

Table 2: Evaluation rubric for the evaluation of the Project.

n	%	Item
1	10	Problem characterization and data collection with a supporting methodology
2	10	Data analysis and generation of results lead to conclusions in the development of the project.
3	10	Evaluation of the problem from multiple perspectives including the connection between different areas and disciplines.
4	10	Demonstrate a comprehensive understanding of the problem to be solved, based on critical thinking and creative solutions.
5	10	Teamwork, effective management and learning through failure.
6	30	Appropriate, innovative and creative technical solution
7	20	Effective presentation and communication of the proposed solution or project

The rubric was developed by researching the best practices found in Weber (2012), in Lăcătuș and Stăiculescu (2016) or Garcia-Barba et al. (2020). Therefore, for the design of the rubric we have considered a holistic view of the development of the project and weighted those items according to the importance they may have when carrying out another successful entrepreneurial project.

In addition, to evaluate the degree of achievement of the objectives regarding the development of soft skills with the realization of the project by the participants, a short questionnaire of satisfaction was carried out with the evaluation of the following questions from 1 to 5, being 1 not at all and 5 very much:

- Have you improved your ability to work in a team?
- Have you improved your conflict resolution skills?
- Have you improved your ability to communicate ideas and concepts?
- Have you improved your ability to adapt your ideas?
- Have you improved your creative capacity and strategic vision?

3 Results

The first aspect to highlight is the positive feedback from the students during the term from a qualitative point of view. All of them have expressed the great practical application of the work proposed for the course and the possibility of using different knowledge from other subjects in the development of the project itself, as well as giving a practical approach to the resolution of the practical part of the course. During the realisation and subsequent defence of the project they work on the five main competences measured. For example, the development of teamwork throughout the whole four-month period, adopting different roles during the project. Creativity and strategic vision to provide solutions to the problems initially posed, as well as the integral conception of the project so that it is technically and economically viable. The ability to communicate, both with colleagues, teachers and collaborating companies, at different levels, is important for the project as well as the resolution of conflicts implicit in any project contextualised in the real world. As I mentioned, these five competences are key to developing an entrepreneurial attitude and valuing entrepreneurship as a job opportunity. Secondly, the average grade of the participating students has improved considerably. The improvement concerning the last academic year without implementation was 16 % (2020-2021) for the first year with the new methodological proposal and 18% for the second year of implementation (2021-2022).

(Figure 4). Students are involved in the subject and the development of the projects by carrying out a realistic, feasible project designed to simulate a future professional activity.

Figure 4. Average grade of the subject for the last three academic years

Finally, the measurement of the results of the perception of the development of soft skills shows the improvement experienced in the last course concerning them. The assessment of the questionnaires shows that the students have experienced the development of these skills (Figure 5).

Communication and Work in teams were the soft skills more developed, followed by a significant level of Creativity and strategic vision. Conflict resolutions and adaptability of ideas were the lesser evaluated skills, but both with a score of 3.8/5.

Figure 5. Mean of the responses to self-assessment questionnaire competencies

4 Conclusions

This research tackles the need for the development of soft skills in civil engineering students, both undergraduate and master's degrees, to promote entrepreneurship and self-employment as a job opportunity, since recent graduates have problems finding their first job. Creativity, collaboration, persuasion and emotional intelligence are the essential soft skills needed.

This work developed a strategy to improve soft skills through the creation of small cooperative teams of students to face different real-life technical problems, establishing alliances with leading companies in the sector and connecting hard and soft skills in line with the syllabus of Maritime Traffic and Port Operation of the Master's degree in Civil Engineering at the University of Alicante.

The results show that by working on the concepts related to the subject, these soft skills can be acquired and developed, becoming more attractive to students. This is reflected in the increase in the average grade of the subject after applying this methodology. Thanks to this, students can increase the number of competencies developed during their academic life at the university.

Finally, it is worth highlighting the usefulness of this work methodology, since all the students consider that they have improved in the entrepreneurial competencies evaluated by means of the self-assessment questionnaire. Therefore, we consider this activity a success as it has improved the job prospects of our students and can also be the beginning of a start-up in an academic environment.

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